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WHITE PAPER

INDIA'S JOURNEY BEYOND COVID-19

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Members of the Consortium

Dr. Arunabha Ghosh, Chief Executive Officer, Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW)

Mr. Chirag Gajjar, Head Subnational Climate Action, Climate, World Resources Institute (WRI) India

Mr. Crispino Lobo, Executive Director, Sampada Trust and Managing Trustee, Watershed Organisation Trust (WOTR)

Dr. Nimish Shah, Managing Director, Toilet Board Coalition

Dr Nitin Pandit, Director at the Ashoka Trust for Research in Ecology and the Environment (ATREE)

Dr. Prashanth N S, Assistant Director (Research), Institute of Public Health, Bengaluru (IPH)

Ms. Perna Singh Bindra, Wildlife Conservationist, Author, and Journalist

Dr. Priya Shyamsundar, Lead Economist, The Nature Conservancy (TNC)

Dr. Uma Ramakrishnan, Molecular Ecologist, National Centre For Biological Sciences, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research (NCBS-TIFR)

Dr. Usha Ramanathan, Researcher, Writer and Social Activist

Editors

Mr. Manoj Kumar, Founder, Social Alpha and Senior Adviser and Head - Institutions, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship, Tata Trusts

Mr. Pradeep Nair, Regional Director India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka, Ford Foundation

Steered by

Dr. Shannon Olsson, Ms. Tina Patrao and Ms. Digangana Mukherjee

the echo network

Centre for Cellular and Molecular Platforms (C-Camp)

UAS-GKVK Campus, Bellary Road,

Bangalore 560 065, Karnataka, India

www.echonetwork.in

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Introduction

The ongoing global pandemic is not only a public health emergency for our country but has aggravated societal challenges, including unemployment and hunger, while precipitating an unprecedented migrant worker crisis. COVID-19¹ ignores geographies, professions, races, and religions. However, it has also highlighted huge inequities in our country that impact our ability to manage this crisis. No matter who we are - we are all one people. We all need access to food, water, energy, shelter, safety, and a future of equal opportunity. Science and technology play an integral role in each of these needs through monitoring and preserving our natural resources, developing a better understanding of our planet, and creating new tools and technologies for our human and environmental ecosystems. **The India that emerges from this crisis needs solutions for society backed by scientific research, enabled by technology, and steeped in innovations that are equitably shared.**

We have the opportunity to reimagine a new India through a holistic approach that incorporates multiple perspectives. Every sector of society has been impacted by COVID-19, and our journey to rejuvenation will require attention to our lands, our lives and our livelihoods equally - ज़मीन भी जान भी और जहां भी. We need to listen to each other, consider different viewpoints, and respond with solutions backed by logic and reasoning. This is what the echo network strives to do. We are a unique social innovation partnership to change the way science is embedded in our society. We facilitate interdisciplinary interactions across sectors to stimulate scientific awareness and encourage science that tackles real-world problems.

This paper represents a group of thought leaders from different walks of life who came together to imagine this path for a New India together. Our consortium engaged in a series of on and offline discussions during May 2020 to identify:

- **Urgent problems created, revealed, or exacerbated by the current crisis (Our Challenges)**
- **Focus areas and measures to rejuvenate our country (Our Compass Points)**
- **Immediate starting points for our path forward (Let's Get Started)**

We discussed an array of societal issues ranging from health care, human rights, economics, to the environment. The consortium arrived at the resultant points as a group, beginning with a list of immediate challenges currently faced by our country. This process induced a progressive consolidation of ideas into focused compass points from which our holistic recommendations were made. Throughout this process, **we have envisioned this pandemic not as an ending, but as the beginning of a new journey. This paper is a unique effort to offer a path forward in an interdisciplinary manner.** We hope that our recommendations regarding health, human dignity, sustainable livelihoods, and secure ecosystems will inspire efforts to widely utilize and apply science and technology for India's bright future.

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

CHAPTER

1

OUR CHALLENGES

1

OUR CHALLENGES

Image by: Nitin Sharma.

The current crisis has exposed a number of challenges that require our urgent attention. In order to understand how science and technology can help address these concerns, we must first identify the challenges we currently face as a country. We have combined the multiple perspectives and experiences of our respective fields to identify the most pressing areas of concern raised during this pandemic.

1. While the country has invested a great deal in cleanliness in recent years, improved and sustained support for hygiene and sanitation is critical. It has been observed that some community and public toilets have been constructed without hand-wash stations or access to piped water or soap. Similarly, operations and maintenance aspects relating to keeping toilets clean, disinfected, safe, and usable need to be addressed. Of equal importance are the needs of the workers who maintain these systems. Proper access to hygiene and sanitation, coupled with both mass awareness and education with community-level engagement and volunteers, can provide immediate benefits in fighting infectious disease.

We require comprehensive and widespread access to hygienic practices and sanitation, combined with awareness and education about hygiene to protect health and prevent illness.

2. Disease emergence is correlated with land-use change. Given India's susceptibility to infectious disease and the link between environmental health, preventive health, and disease burden, a national health agenda requires joint action using the OneHealth approach. OneHealth is a strategy for collaboration and communication between multiple sectors to simultaneously address the health of humans, animals, and the environment. This pandemic highlights the disconnect among human, environmental, animal, and

wildlife health on the one hand, and implementers, decision-makers, and academia on the other hand. We must integrate measures and technologies to prevent and respond to disease outbreaks and leverage actions across multiple sectors.

We need to build a public health strategy with rural and urban primary health centres and schools as empowered focal points of a OneHealth approach to address disease outbreaks such that any new signs of infectious disease are quickly and appropriately tackled.

3. We need more public investment and allocation for health care in India with a technically sound regulatory architecture that relies on high-quality evidence and is grounded in achieving equitable health. We must trigger state and local government interest and engagement in health as a public good and not a matter left to the private sector. In addition, we urgently need to address the lack of formal public health training in India's health workforce. While the current pandemic is a health and humanitarian crisis, its treatment as a law and order situation meant that the first point of contact was the police rather than sufficient numbers of trained ground-level administrators and health professionals. For COVID-19¹ and any vaccine-preventable disease, we need both investment in the research and development of vaccines and treatments, as well as defined policies for fair and equitable access during their development and distribution, as prescribed by the Nuffield Council on Bioethics.

We must invest in decentralized, accessible, and comprehensive public health care through widespread investments in PHC¹ infrastructure that offsets current inequities, including burdens on the few large government and non-profit or private hospitals.

4. The economic lockdown, coupled with underlying structural changes, differential urban-rural development, and persistent social norms that promote inequity and marginalization of migrant labourers resulted in mass migration during this crisis. While decentralization and labour registration and regulation is valuable as a systemic measure, the systems might not be in place to meet immediate needs. This calls for providing shelter, cash, or food depending on need through various local and federal institutions. The State is constitutionally and morally obliged to protect life.

We must urgently manage the unprecedented current migration via cash payments, shelter, food, and supplies as needed from the PDS¹ for a minimum of three months while industrial and agricultural activity is being restarted. In parallel, we need to reinforce the rights and protections of labour.

5. Our urban poor need immediate social protection. This could involve the supply of water for health and hygiene, mobile health clinics where health care access is limited, food delivery in partnership with NGOs¹ and community groups, cash assistance or rent compensation, and creation of social safety net systems equivalent to rural public works programs focused on the urban poor.

We require programmes and efforts that address the needs of the urban poor with the help of decentralized local administration and services.

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

6. There has been a persistent marginalization of our citizenry resulting in exploitation, dispensability, and forced displacement. We must recognize who and where our citizens are, their interests and needs, their role in society, and their living conditions. We must actively recognize that all our citizens play a vital role in our success as a country and that no one is redundant or irrelevant in our economy or communities.

We must address the inequality, ideas of dispensability, redundancy, and invisibilizing of people and their problems as well as strengthen their civil rights and liberties, including freedom of movement and rights to food, work, business, and dignity.

7. Information technologies can be excellent tools to disseminate information and maintain transparency for people, but the digital divide must be recognized. Technology cannot be a substitute for active mediation between people and the State, which is better achieved through strengthening ground-level administration as mediators.

We must address the impact of technology on individual and collective rights and freedoms, including surveillance, exclusion, and the digital divide.

8. Short-term actions such as ensuring food security and subsidizing energy use are currently needed for humanitarian reasons and to jump-start the economy. There are opportunities to achieve both economic recovery and environmental benefits in areas of restoration that offer job relief and long-term outcomes. However, these efforts can also produce macroeconomic trade-offs and job conversion.

We must take immediate steps to meet this year's harvesting and planting requirements to ensure food security and subsidize actions and technologies that reduce water and electricity use, emissions, and air pollution.

9. The importance of a green recovery is vital for the country, and MSME's will play a key role. MSMEs have experienced a cash flow problem with delays in payments and receivables for which we lack data to shape appropriate responses. Banks are also often unwilling to on-lend to MSMEs. Efforts to boost jobs and growth must begin with a long-term vision for how MSMEs will be reinvigorated after the lockdown period.

We need to enact decentralized economic reforms that assist small businesses (including farmers), including paying all government and public sector outstanding dues, providing cheap, low-interest business credit, and a time-bound credit guarantee by the government on incremental loans to induce financial institutions to lend to MSMEs. We need strategies that will allow MSMEs to explore environmental challenges as business opportunities coupled with the economic reforms.

10. In India, about 60% of the total net sown area comes under rainfed lands. These areas also provide the largest number of low-paid migrant labour to cities and industrial sectors who have been severely affected by this pandemic.

We must improve farmers' livelihoods and promote local agricultural value chains to enable farmers to capture a greater share of the value generated.

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

11. Following this crisis, it may be perceived as easier and faster to invest in large infrastructure projects to create jobs. A more targeted green-economy approach might take more time and effort, given the need for immediate relief. Such efforts can also impact currently employed people in sectors that will be altered by this transition, including mining and fossil fuels. However, it is critical to evaluate the negative social and ecological impacts of development, such as linear intrusions, hydroelectric projects, and mining on biodiversity, ecosystems, and ensuing economic loss.

We must build a resilient economy through employment generation and securing agriculture (and allied activities) by immediately restarting public works programmes, coupled with long-term planning and process reforms and enhanced financial outlays. Nature positive and climate mitigating employment opportunities, such as ecological restoration of lands or decentralized energy solutions accompanied by sustainable and equitable governance of natural resources could create jobs, bolster economies, and benefit local people.

12. India is a predicted hotspot for disease emergence because of its high human population density, intense and aggressive land-use change, and loss of biodiversity. The nature-human balance has been severely disrupted because of unchecked and unsustainable development. The country's law enforcement must more effectively enable the protection and safeguard of our environments, wildlife, and forests, while ensuring effective implementation of environment, forest, and wildlife laws. With economic growth, there will be more risk of land and biodiversity loss to promote economic activities rather than

embracing ecosystems as enablers of growth. Changes in land use, wildlife trade, and climate change bring wildlife, livestock, and humans into closer contact. This facilitates the spread of disease. As the pandemic shows, such disease emergence degrades public health, disrupts social systems, and reduces the prospects for economic growth.

We need to restore the nature-human balance by identifying and monitoring hotspots for possible disease emergence, strengthening laws for the environment, forest protection, wildlife protection, and biodiversity conservation, and enabling restoration to maximise ecosystem services that involve and benefit local people. Development and land use must be planned to minimise disease emergence.

13. As India looks to reopen its economy, now is the opportunity to reflect upon systemic actions needed for a more sustainable and resilient economy with much-needed investment in infrastructure and development to boost the Indian economy. Rapid development will cause devastation to ecological systems, and dwindling ecosystems induce pandemics and natural disasters. Such linear growth has already adversely affected climate, ecology, and biodiversity. The future may see greater employment in the gig economy and e-commerce with new technologies for response and resilience. While supporting the development of such sectors, proper regulations should minimize environmental trade-offs.

We need to reimagine models of economic planning and development that inherently value and protect ecosystems, account for their services, and integrate environmental strategies.

CHAPTER

2

OUR COMPASS POINTS

PREVENTIVE AND
RESPONSIVE
PUBLIC HEALTH
SYSTEMS

COMMUNITIES
WITH DIGNITY
AND EQUITY

SECURE
HUMAN AND
ENVIRONMENTAL
ECOSYSTEMS

SUSTAINABLE
LIVELIHOODS

Image by: Shreeneet Rathi

2

OUR COMPASS POINTS

After recognizing crucial points of concern, we must characterize larger areas of focus and diagnose measures to mitigate further complications and maintain a clear course of action. The challenges mentioned have been summarized into four compass points guiding potential paths forward using existing or innovative mechanisms in our country. Here we offer a holistic discussion of these health, human rights, economic and environmental strategies, with an aim to determine where and how science and technology can help lead to their realization.

1. Preventive and responsive public health systems
2. Communities with dignity and equity
3. Sustainable livelihoods
4. Secure human and environmental ecosystems

1. Preventive and Responsive Public Health Systems

Life expectancy has steadily increased in India over the past 100 years and now stands above 70 years.

Nevertheless, this is still in the bottom 30% of the world, in large part due to persistent morbidity from multiple sources — disease, nutrition, accidents, and access to health care. Each of these risks may alone appear to have a relatively low probability, but when a large event such as this global pandemic occurs, the impacts can be catastrophic. Furthermore, several of these risks compound each other and can quickly

overwhelm our capacity to respond to crises. For example, increased temperatures resulting from climate change exacerbate both vector-borne disease, reduce food security and access to water, and directly induce heatstroke and other injuries. The quick and swift actions of certain states in dealing with public health crises have been exemplary regarding public health administration and the citizenry. Informed and aware citizens, equipped with simple interventions such as access to soap and other hygienic needs can play a substantial role in mitigating public health challenges. Simultaneously, several of these health challenges can be prevented through attention to the human-ecosystem interface combined with access to basic needs and health care that increase wellness and immunity. A health emergency should never escalate into a law and order issue where those in distress report to the police rather than healthcare professionals.

Despite this urgent need, India's total health expenditure is only a third of the world's average. Much of this expenditure involves the private health sector and is oriented towards new digital efforts such as

telemedicine, digital payments, and the National Health Stack. Higher allocation for public health in terms of human, provisional, and physical infrastructure is needed. First, **we require a careful diagnostic assessment of disease and accident risk faced by people across Indian states, and the environmental, agricultural, and livelihood sources of risk.** This preventive approach should map critical vulnerabilities in different geographies and resources. **We require decentralized and intersectoral action for humans, livestock, wildlife, forests, and water to prevent and respond to infectious disease. This also necessitates a clear articulation of the role of science and technology for studying these interrelated factors that can lead to disease outbreaks.** A substantial funding component can establish research, and the subsequent science can impact policy for OneHealth based programmes. In addition, we need to urgently address the lack of formal public health training in India by creating nodal public health training and research institutions in each district of the country.

OneHealth is an integrative approach that simultaneously addresses human, animal, and environmental health to prevent, detect, and respond to infectious disease and other health issues. The approach uses tools such as surveillance and reporting to improve health security and achieve gains in development. Graphics adapted from Operational Framework for Strengthening Human, Animal, and Environmental Public Health Systems at their Interface.

Second, we must address both health care and health systems. The former involves the accessibility, quality, and delivery of services. The latter requires multilevel financing, governance, and promotion of integrated and intersectoral action on health through science-based approaches such as OneHealth.

We need a roadmap for systemic investments in primary health care that ensures access to preventive, curative, and rehabilitative services for every citizen regardless of region or socio-economic status. This should include widespread investments in infrastructure, equipment, and provisions, a capacitated health workforce, a system of disease surveillance based on OneHealth principles, and strong health governance with a cadre of public health professionals rather than specialist doctors who currently are in charge of public health. We further require a substantially larger financial outlay for safe, effective, and quality health care services by improving primary and secondary care at the district level. This should include local programs to provide education on nutrition, safety, and hygiene. There is guidance available in the [High Level Expert Group on Universal Health Coverage](#), the [National Mission on Biodiversity and Human Well Being](#), the [Sustainable Development Goals](#), and the [Global Health Security Agenda](#) provide specific targets and indicators. The MoHFW¹ and the ICMR¹, along with state and Panchayat level governance, will play a central responsibility for such efforts.

2. Communities with Dignity and Equity

Any systemic solution must start by acknowledging the marginalization and stratification in our country to ensure a system that works for everyone. The current crisis has revealed stark inequities with our population asked to stay home and practice physical distancing and so many without homes, food, or water. Many more live in crowded spaces without access to proper sanitation and hygiene to protect themselves from illness. This disparity forced many to migrate, with no record of

who or where they are, and no means to provide direct assistance. Such inequity has created a humanitarian crisis that endangers the entire population and must be faced head-on if we are to make progress on any issue we have raised. Our communities — and governance systems — will increasingly struggle to cope with a perfect storm of shocks. We need infusion and enforcement of safety nets for our people.

We must develop decentralized systems of public service delivery and distribution that are evidence-based and data-driven, including local government reforms and national level investments that can address a dynamic citizenry.

A high-level task force comprising institutes such as [FM](#)¹, [RBI](#)¹, and [ISI](#)¹ can identify socio-economic data gaps. A register of employment should be mandated at the lowest administrative levels of business to reach people in times of need. Labour rights and laws that promote safe and secure working environments for all types of workers must be enforced or reformed without compromising individual rights. A series of recommendations are available in the [2017 Working Group on Migration](#), and the [Interstate Migrant Workmen's Act of 1979](#) needs enforcement. These efforts require a shared leadership. A decentralized representation must be pursued. Local and city-level governments should be strengthened to provide health and safety directly to their residents. A series of commissions at central and state levels with public representation should examine current inequities and provide recommendations for improvements. Technology should not replace accessibility at the expense of direct communication. Reforms in education and governance, such as those in Kerala, have shown long term benefits for health and well-being, and could embolden efforts in other areas of the country. All of these efforts can improve the accessibility and delivery of essential health and human services through transparent and decentralized means.

Infectious disease, climate and land-use change, and poverty will continue to challenge our nation, and we must strengthen our social protection policies

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

REASONS AND STREAMS OF INTERCENSAL MIGRATION (NUMBERS IN MILLIONS, DATA FROM CENSUS 2011)

India on the Move- According to the most recent data from Census 2011, there are at least 454 million migrants in India. While marriage remains a major source of migration, the growing share of family migration may indicate the increase in families accompanying migrant workers. This data also does not reflect short term or seasonal migration that is increasing with the number of urban centres and their accessibility. Data obtained from the *Report of the working group on Migration*.

and practices for inevitable times of distress. A livelihood protection fund where employers set aside a small portion of profit currently allocated to CSR¹ can assist workers during employment discontinuity for 3-6 months. Central and State governments should also establish funding at the district level to support citizens affected by public emergencies or economic downturn. Investments in public works programmes and the development of urban alternatives are needed to support these efforts. Public works programmes such as NREGA¹, restoring ecology and ecosystems, agri-infrastructure, PMKSY¹, water resources development programmes, and water conservation must immediately be restored, especially in aspirational districts and districts with high tribal, returning migrant, or daily wage worker populations. If these jobs can restore degraded lands through watershed and springshed development, waterbody or mangrove restoration, terracing, appropriate cropping patterns, sustainable climate-resilient agriculture (especially rainfed), or

integrated water management practices involving groundwater, there will be additional long-term benefits.

3. Sustainable Livelihoods

India has multiple successful examples of distributed and targeted market linkages that have established wealth, prosperity, and self-sufficiency for communities, such as the Amul experiment, SEWA¹, FabIndia, and others. However, the trinity of jobs, growth, and sustainability are often treated as mutually exclusive in terms of public policy. For example, solar parks offer sustainability and growth but create fewer job opportunities than a distributed energy infrastructure. **Many successful examples of distributed market linkages can inspire us to rebuild the economy with**

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

SEWA

SEWA, a trade union registered in 1972, is a movement to provide sustainable livelihoods for women. Currently, SEWA boasts more than 1.4 million members across 13 Indian states. SEWA Bharat aims to extend support to women informal workers across India to obtain work, income, food and social security.

Source: sewabharat.org

STATES	MEMBERS TILL 2016
Assam	384
Bihar	1,00,000
Delhi	52,000
Gujarat	7,34,729
Jammu & Kashmir	752
Kerala	15,000
Madhya Pradesh	3,54,843

STATES	MEMBERS TILL 2016
Maharashtra	1,492
Meghalaya	500
Rajasthan	54,540
Uttar Pradesh	1,03,067
Uttrakhand	24,200
West Bengal	18,378

Fabindia

Fabindia is a fair trade Indian apparel company established in 1960 that connects over

55,000
traditional village artisans

from rural areas to urban markets in order to promote sustainable rural employment while preserving India's traditional handicrafts.

Source: fabindia.com

Amul

Amul, founded in 1946, provides livelihoods to 3.6 million milk producers in villages across Gujarat including

1.2 million women

Amul started as a cooperative of dairy farmers and grew to become a household name. The success of the Amul model was replicated across the country under the Operation Flood program, making India the 9th largest and world's fastest-growing producers of milk.

Source: aphrdi.ap.gov.in

18559 Village Dairy Co-op. Societies of Gujarat state

23 MLPD*
milk procure from
3.6 million
farmers

* Megalitre Per Day

a united focus on jobs, growth, and sustainability. In rural areas, entrepreneurship development programmes can encourage enterprises that employ people and support the village ecosystem through tourism, agri-enterprises, artisans, and textiles. Distributed and decentralised energy, water and sanitation infrastructure, sustainable cooling, regenerative agriculture, and rural livelihood activities can support both rural and urban economies. Human, livestock, and agri-residue wastes can be treated as resources for conversion to energy or nutrients for farms and can spur low carbon economic growth. In turn, these

efforts are more environmentally sustainable, climate-sensitive, and have higher employment coefficients to deliver resilience and sustainability. These new sources of growth can be promoted by capital support to rural entrepreneurs, market assessment to connect entrepreneurs to new customers, technical assistance to help enterprises prepare documentation to get access to investment and credit, and training for technical and non-technical commercial activities to help start-ups scale operations in rural areas.

To rejuvenate our economies, we must facilitate the marketing and transport of goods and services and their supporting infrastructure. Localizing the movement of products and services based on urban, peri-urban, and rural needs can focus the delivery of particular commodities to a specific geography. We must support economic, social, and environmental links between these regions by strengthening national and regional development planning. **We need to enact decentralized evidence-based reforms that assist small businesses (including farmers) including paying all government and public sector outstanding dues to MSMEs¹, a time-bound credit guarantee by the government on incremental loans to induce financial institutions to lend to MSMEs, and providing cheap, low-interest credit to promote climate-friendly business practices in waste management, energy generation, grid development, mobility, sustainable agriculture, and clean R&D.** This also includes legal and enforcement overhaul to support and protect small enterprises and workers alike. The unorganized sector contributes nearly half of our GDP¹ and must be provided with safer and cleaner technologies with time-bound incentives and protections so that MSMEs¹ can thrive and grow. During times of economic downturn or distress, banks are often unwilling to on-lend to MSMEs¹, so an enhanced credit guarantee is needed. Finally, **we must improve farmers' livelihoods and promote local agricultural value chains to enable farmers to capture a more significant share of the value generated by considering the potential of fully opening up trade in agricultural commodities and allowing direct and free trading by considering changes to APMC¹, as has been recently acknowledged.**

Importantly, **such rejuvenation also requires the establishment of new skills and entrepreneurs across India.** We must improve our public education to meet these emerging opportunities and establish more capacity building programs. We need a new social compact where key priority areas of the economy and job opportunities are highlighted for training, particularly for sectors that will soon be displaced by new technologies and innovations. A collaboration

of industry, education, and government can provide pedagogical and technological training for the production, use, and repair of new technologies and services. We must build and nurture interdisciplinary spaces with active participation from Indian youth where science, technology, social sciences, and policy can intersect to generate new ideas. With so many governmental and non-profit institutions for education, there is an enormous potential to integrate science, technology, and society at early education levels to foster interdisciplinary thinking, ethical civic engagement, and skilling for our progressing economy.

4. Secure Human and Environmental Ecosystems

The previous focus areas have emphasized the importance of our ecosystems for health, safety, livelihoods, and the economy. Our ecosystems encompass not only our environments and natural resources, but our insects, wildlife, forests, deserts, grasslands, wetlands, water bodies, and mountains. Their ecosystem services persist far beyond rural communities to all Indians who eat food grown in fertile lands sustained by wild pollinators and soil microbes, drink water fed from protected waterways and forests, and are shielded from heat, drought, and inclement weather by our forests and mangroves. This creates a circularity where adaptive stewardship of biodiversity and ecosystems is an essential part of our survival. We must ensure **appropriate environmental safeguards and compliance to existing environment laws for clean, unpolluted air, water, and soil critical for human and environmental health and security.**

Immense knowledge of environmental issues and ecosystems remains undocumented for Indian systems. **Modern scientific knowledge, traditional ecological knowledge, and sustainable development goals can be combined into a roadmap that prevents**

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

environmental degradation. This roadmap can forecast, predict, and alert emerging challenges and disasters, including infectious disease. This roadmap must assess biodiversity loss and climate change impacts across the Indian subcontinent and predict possible areas of disease emergence and ecosystem

ecosystems for non-forestry purposes. Such efforts must also recalibrate costs from pollution, climate change, deforestation, and land degradation. Any proposed development impinging on protected or biodiverse areas must involve rigorous environmental and economic assessment incorporating costs, benefits,

service loss and its health and economic impacts on people. This research should be coupled with increased funding for local monitoring and management that involves citizens and local communities, requiring country-wide ecological awareness and education. Initiatives such as the [National Mission on Biodiversity and Human Well Being](#) can assist this process. In parallel, **we require effective science-guided implementation of laws protecting environments, forests, and wildlife that halt the diversion and fragmentation of protected areas and other natural**

and alternate scenarios. These assessments should include multiple stakeholders and be assessed by independent experts in a transparent and inclusive process.

Agriculture is fundamental to India's food security and will continue to support a large number of livelihoods. To make Indian agriculture competitive, we must strengthen the ecosystems where agriculture is conducted. Agricultural output ultimately depends on the quality of services that the ecosystem can provide.

We must increase financial allocations and research for science-based solutions that foster integrated watershed development projects, promote nature-friendly, climate-responsive agriculture, upgrade skills, enhance technology adoption across the agriculture value chain, invest in post-harvest value chains, and equip farmers to progressively increase participation for better incomes. Erstwhile integrated watershed development programs incorporated some of these ideas and should now be accordingly revitalized and expanded to other ecosystem services such as forests, grasslands, wetlands, and wildlife.

Reimagining environmental strategies requires us to change our mindset of “saving nature” as an economic burden to incorporating ecosystems into our economic planning and development. **We need to reimagine models of development by employing a data-driven environmental strategy, including systemic evaluation of adverse ecological impacts wherever possible, making sector-specific measures conditional upon ecosystem protection, and developing a comprehensive strategy.** These efforts require a long-term change in behaviour that strengthens

existing environmental standards, assesses stimulus packages from ecological perspectives, and strengthens resource efficiency standards. Development activities and infrastructure such as dams and highways should include ecological, economical, and social cost-benefit analysis. Factoring a life cycle perspective into infrastructure and industry planning can better incorporate the benefits of ecological goods and services. We must examine both the supply and demand sides of resource management to balance productivity with sustainability and integrate elements of the value chain and market into agriculture, business, and industry. Direct benefits can also be provided through short-term jobs supporting watershed development, river and wetland clean-up, ecological restoration, and other efforts. At the same time, securing our ecosystems must be performed with minimal impacts on tribal and forest-associated communities while keeping in view their livelihoods and cultures. Incorporating traditional knowledge systems into modern innovations can produce unique and relevant outputs for our economy.

CHAPTER

3

LET'S GET STARTED

3

LET'S GET
STARTED

We must begin the path to a healthier, more resilient India. We need to act swiftly and decisively. The following starting points are diagnostic, rather than prescriptive. In particular, we highlight how science and technology can help in addressing each point. We further hope these suggestions can be integrated with recent national efforts such as the [Consultation process for new Science, Technology, and Innovation Policy \(STIP\)](#). Guided by our compass points, we recommend the following immediate starting points for our journey towards our future India:

1. Enhance public expenditure for responsive health systems based on intersectoral action using OneHealth approaches, requiring a scientific understanding of the relationship between human, animal, and environmental health in India. Make primary health centres the focal point for improving community health through increasing capacity-building investments in a responsive public health workforce.

2. Embrace a OneHealth approach for prevention through intersectoral disease surveillance and decentralised rapid feedback and response systems stemming from primary health centres. This evidence-based and data-driven approach should also ensure goals of the [Swachh Bharat Mission](#) and related national health, hygiene, and sanitation programs.

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

3. Strengthen short-term stabilising efforts, including decentralized cash payments for recently unemployed workers, MSME¹ salary support, expansion of NREGA¹ to at least 200 days for the creation of rural assets, consideration of an urban equivalent of NREGA, and universalization of PDS¹ to allow transient workers and manual labour to benefit. Research that gathers, assesses, and predicts socio-economic outcomes in relation to the other recommendations can help mitigate a future need for these stabilizing efforts.

4. Initiate a pivot in our views on human rights as necessitated by the migrant crisis. The Interstate Migrant Workmen's Act must be activated with state registration and contractor responsibility for reporting who and where workers are with evidence-based planning and data science, and assigning legal responsibility for their work and welfare. Employers and states should be responsible for worker rights to avoid the exploitation of labour.

5. Strengthen transparency and community participation in decision-making related to resource use, public services, and investments through increased decentralization. Improve scientific communication and education to allow communities to obtain and assess data directly from its source. Communities should participate in prioritizing investments for sustainable solutions, and commissions can be developed to provide localized input.

6. Engage science and technology to tap into greenfield opportunities for jobs, growth, and sustainability in rural and urban areas that can attract new investments, have high employment coefficients, and are socially, environmentally, and ecologically sustainable. Such projects may include distributed energy systems, distributed water and sanitation infrastructure, renewable energy, farm nutrients from human, livestock and agri-residue wastes, sustainable cold chains, and sustainable climate-smart agriculture.

7. Improve the resilience of our lands by increasing financial allocations and research for science-based solutions that foster integrated watershed and springshed development projects, promote nature-neutral, climate-responsive agriculture, upgrade skills and enhance technology adoption across agriculture value chains, invest in post-harvest value chains, and equip farmers to progressively increase participation for better incomes.

8. Immediately conduct a skill and livelihood opportunity mapping exercise to identify and match current local economic opportunities, upgrade existing skills to access higher income levels, and align new skills with emerging opportunities. Institutionalise collaborative partnership platforms and regularly review functioning at local levels involving stakeholders from different sectors with clearly defined outcomes and resource provisioning commitments and incentives.

9. Stringently enforce existing environmental laws and regulations to prevent further ecosystem destruction and degradation and reimagine landscapes through a science-based restoration of natural habitats and environmental management that maximizes ecosystem services and sustainability.

10. Encourage biodiversity research that helps prioritise landscapes and conservation in the country to ensure the preservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services to reduce health and livelihood risks.

11. Mainstream ecological and environmental concerns backed by scientific research in the planning and development process. Factor these components into GDP¹ calculation to account for the benefits of ecosystem services and costs of their losses.

¹ See Glossary of Abbreviations

Conclusions

COVID-19¹ is not a health crisis, but an existential one. It has challenged who we are as a country, and who we want to be. India has a remarkable capacity to meet this crisis head-on. We have the ability to emerge from this challenging period in our shared history as an inspiration for the entire planet. But reaching that potential requires us to work together and recognize that our future depends on the well-being of both our land and all people who live on it. We must learn to communicate not as businessmen, farmers, scientists, politicians, or doctors, but as one people of India. Science and technology will serve an integral role in our future. Science helps us measure, assess, and analyse our planet. And technology can help us to live better in

our world. The time has come for us to see that the art of scientific discourse and debate belongs everywhere in society. Science and technology innovations have the potential to drive positive social, economic, and environmental change. Interdisciplinary research incorporating our lands, our lives, and our livelihoods together will ensure that this impact is sustainable and equitable. **The pandemic has steered us towards a new beginning, giving us the opportunity to combine our interdisciplinary viewpoints into a unified path forward.** We must learn to listen to each other and generate trust. **We are all one people, on one path towards India's future.**

¹See Glossary of Abbreviations

Glossary of Abbreviations

APMC - Agricultural Produce Market Committee

COVID-19 - Coronavirus Disease 2019, or 2019-nCoV

CSR - Corporate Social Responsibility

FM - Financial Modeling Institute

GDP - Gross Domestic Product

ICMR - Indian Council of Medical Research

ISI - Indian Statistical Institute

MoHFW - Ministry of Health and Family Welfare,
Government of India

MSME - Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

NREGA - National Rural Employment Guarantee Act,
2005

PDS - Public Distribution System

NGO - Non-Governmental Organization

PHC - Primary Health Care

PMKSY - Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana

RBI - Reserve Bank of India

SEWA - Self Employed Women's Association

Centre for Cellular and Molecular Platforms (C-Camp)
UAS-GKVK Campus, Bellary Road,
Bangalore 560 065, Karnataka, India
info@echonetnetwork.in | +91 9740201407